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DEVELOPMENT OF MODERN MARKETING APPROACHES TO CUSTOMER RELATIONSHIP MANAGEMENT IN RETAIL ENTERPRISES

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Abstract. This article examines modern marketing approaches to customer relationship management in retail enterprises. The study analyzed the theoretical and practical aspects of digital marketing tools, an omnichannel service model, personalized recommendation systems, and loyalty programs. The importance of CRM systems in the process of digital transformation was substantiated using the example of the Uzbek retail market. The effectiveness of data-driven management, customer segmentation, and omnichannel integration was highlighted using the example of the Uzum and Korzinka enterprises. The results of the study showed that the use of a single customer profile, personalized marketing, and digital ecosystems can increase customer loyalty and the competitiveness of retail enterprises.

Keywords: CRM, retail, digital marketing, omnichannel service, customer loyalty, personalization, e-commerce, digital transformation.

INTRODUCTION

The retail sector is steadily strengthening its market position as one of the promising sectors in the global economy. Consumer behavior has changed radically under the influence of the digital environment: the purchase process is now dependent not only on product and price indicators, but also on experience, convenience, personalization of information and the quality of interaction. Such new conditions require retail enterprises to abandon traditional marketing models and adopt modern approaches aimed at building long-term relationships with customers. The concept of Customer Relationship Management (CRM) has begun a new stage in marketing theory as an expression of this need [4].

The retail sector in Uzbekistan has been showing steady growth dynamics in recent years. According to official data from the National Statistics Committee, in January-October 2025, retail turnover in our republic reached 356.6 trillion soums, an increase of 10.3% compared to the same period last year; the total number of active retail enterprises amounted to 85,585 units [1]. Positive changes in this direction are inextricably linked to the increase in the consumption potential of the country's population, the formation of a middle class, and the expansion of the level of use of digital services. It is these factors that increase the need for systematic tools that serve to redirect marketing approaches towards the consumer.

The share of digital platforms in the retail market is rapidly expanding. According to international analytical reports, in 2024 the volume of e-commerce in the country was equal to 1.2 billion US dollars, which is about 3.8% of the retail market; by 2027 its share is forecast to increase to 9-11% [3]. Such rapid growth sharply increases the need for tools for systematic, information-based and dynamic management of customer relationships in retail. The importance of CRM systems is beginning to be perceived not only as one of the operational tools of marketing, but also as a central element of the enterprise strategy [9].

The purpose of the study was to summarize modern marketing approaches to customer relationship management in retail enterprises on a scientific basis and reveal their compatibility with the experience of Uzbekistan. In order to achieve the set goal, the theoretical and practical possibilities of digital marketing tools, an omnichannel service model, personalized recommendation systems and loyalty programs were considered. The results of the study will serve to enrich the scientific knowledge base aimed at improving marketing strategies in the context of the digital transformation of the national retail market.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The idea of customer relationship management in marketing theory began to take shape systematically in the late 1990s. Initially, the concept of CRM was understood as a technological tool intended for sales and service departments, but over time it turned into a strategic concept of the enterprise, covering the complex scope of customer value management. This was clearly demonstrated by the classic studies of Romano and Fjermestad; the authors described electronic CRM as a new paradigm of marketing strategy and predicted its increasing importance for a wide range of related disciplines [5]. Research in recent years has confirmed this point of view with empirical evidence.

The essence of the modern CRM concept has become increasingly intertwined with technological infrastructure. The digital era has enabled CRM to be integrated with artificial intelligence, big data analytics, cloud computing, and mobile applications, enabling businesses to offer personalized customer experiences in real time [4]. This integration has transformed CRM from a traditional transactional tool to a strategic communication platform, with Relationship Marketing Theory, Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Digital Interaction Theory serving as conceptual foundations. Leading platforms such as Salesforce, HubSpot, and others have taken the quality of business-customer relationships to a new level with predictive analytics and omnichannel integration tools.

Omnichannel has become a central theme for retail CRM. Empirical research by Hyeon Jo and Youngsok Bang has shown that consumer loyalty in an omnichannel environment is determined by a number of mediating factors, including relevance of information, personalization of the offer, and satisfaction [7]. An extended survey of 4,418 respondents in Finland and Sweden confirmed the positive impact of personalization and hedonic motivation on the cognitive and emotional components of the customer experience; experience quality, in turn, contributed to the sustainability of loyalty indicators [6]. These findings provide further insight into the multidimensional nature of customer value in marketing.

The integration of artificial intelligence and machine learning technologies into CRM systems has become a priority area of research for a new generation. In their 2025 study, Roosta and colleagues proposed an intelligent analytical framework that empirically demonstrated the ability to predict customer loyalty based on purchasing behavior, sociocultural factors, and learning techniques. This framework was aimed at optimizing pricing, inventory, and personalized advertising decisions by increasing the efficiency of CRM modules within enterprise information systems (EIS) [8]. A bibliometric study based on VOSviewer, which summarized the stages of CRM development, found that satisfaction, loyalty, and public relations remained the leading thematic blocks, but artificial intelligence, big data, and e-commerce were gradually emerging as independent scientific areas [11].

The latest generation of CRM research focuses on the emotional and social dimensions of customer experience. An analysis of 1,025 scientific articles using the Latent Dirichlet Allocation method identified six main trends in CRM development: experience, organization, satisfaction, loyalty, utility, and community [9]. This topology reflects the fact that CRM is no longer understood as transaction management, but as a tool for building brand communities, deepening customer emotional connections, and building long-term partnerships. Such approaches have also begun to be systematically studied in the domestic scientific literature; in particular, B. Safarov's research on the formation of a retail marketing system has made an important contribution to the empirical assessment of the effectiveness of digital platforms and loyalty tools in a national context [10].

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to ensure the quality and evidence-based methodological basis of the study, a combination of several complementary scientific methods was used. First, through the documentary method, the official retail turnover data published by the National Statistics Committee of the Republic of Uzbekistan [1], the industry review prepared by the Investment Consulting Management Company [15], and the industry analytical report prepared by KPMG Caucasus and Central Asia [2] were systematically summarized. Second, using the comparative analysis method, the differences between modern CRM paradigms, namely the classic transaction-centric model, the digital integration model, and the model based on artificial intelligence, were revealed.

The empirical part of the study consisted of a secondary content analysis based on published open sources. The objects of empirical analysis were the leading retail and e-commerce entities in Uzbekistan - the Korzinka network and the Uzum digital ecosystem; their corporate reports, investment statements, and analytical materials in industry publications were studied in detail [12]. Content analysis identified structural dimensions for the five stages of CRM strategy - data collection, segmentation, personalization, channel management, and loyalty programs. The data obtained through the analysis were organized through theoretical generalization and synthesis, and ultimately expressed in the form of the author's conceptual model. All sources used belonged to

approved categories such as publications in the Scopus index, corporate official documents, and government statistics.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

The dynamics of retail turnover in Uzbekistan indicate that a broad economic space is being formed for the systematic management of customer relations. According to official statistics, In January-February 2025, retail trade turnover reached 57,100.1 billion soums, an increase of 10.2% compared to the same period last year; in January-May 2025, the figure was 163,713.6 billion soums, with a growth rate of 9.2% [15]. In the months leading up to the end of the year, until October, turnover increased to 356.6 trillion soums, with growth strengthening to 10.3% [1]. The dynamics indicated not only the increasing consumption potential of the population, but also the structural expansion of the industry.

Qualitative changes in the market structure also require the industry to adapt to new marketing approaches. According to a KPMG report, the volume of e-commerce in the country was \$311 million in 2022 and is projected to reach \$1.8-2.2 billion by 2027; the average annual growth rate is 41.4-47.4 percent [2]. Consumers spend 35 percent of their online purchases on household appliances and electronics, and 19 percent on fashion products; and the fact that 60 percent of the country's population is under 30 years old ensures the rapid spread of a mobile-based consumer culture [3]. Such demographics create a broad basis for omnichannel CRM models (Table 1).

Table 1
Some indicators of the retail and e-commerce market in Uzbekistan¹

Indicator	Value	Period	Source
Retail turnover, trillion soums	356.6	January-October 2025	Stat.uz [1]
Number of active retail enterprises, units	85 585	As of November 1, 2025	Stat.uz [1]
E-commerce volume, billion US dollars	1.2	2024	Trade.gov [3]
E-commerce forecast (CAGR), annual percentage	41.4-47.4	2022-2027	KPMG [2]
Uzum monthly users, million people	17<	2025	Trade.gov [3]
Uzum GMV, million USD	500	2025	TechCrunch [14]
Korzinka strategic investment, \$110 million		2025	Pivot.uz [13]

One of the most striking examples of the local market is the experience of the Uzum digital ecosystem. By the end of 2025, the company's GMV amounted to 500 million US dollars, net income reached 176 million US dollars, and the annual number of ecosystem users approached 20 million. The company's marketplace division works with 17 thousand local sellers, and the platform's payment turnover amounted to 11 billion US dollars; its internal banking network served 5 million customers, creating one in every two debit cards issued in the country in 2025 [14]. These indicators confirmed the feasibility of the CRM approach not only as a separate module, but also as a digital ecosystem that covers the entire organizational structure.

The practical scope of digital transformation is further illustrated by the example of Korzinka, a leading player in the classic retail segment. In 2025, a preferential investment of \$110 million from the Abu Dhabi and Omani investment funds was aimed at strengthening the supermarket segment, expanding the Korzinka Mahalla neighborhood store network, and developing the Korzinka Go e-commerce platform; this was accompanied

¹ Source: compiled by the author based on official statistical publications and corporate reports.

by the construction of a 49,000 square meter Class A distribution center [13]. The company plans to reach more than 1,000 stores in the medium term and turn Korzinka Go into a leading e-grocery platform. It is in this strategic plan that the integration of traditional and digital sales formats within a single CRM is of great importance.

A comparative analysis of the Uzum and Korzinka experiences shows that the architectures of the digital ecosystem and the supermarket chain are increasingly adopting complementary customer relationship management models. The former has integrated express delivery, BNPL lending and payment services into a single interface, forming a comprehensive database that analyzes the customer's daily transactional behavior. The latter, by combining a physical store network, small points in the neighboring mahalla format and e-commerce services on a single logistics infrastructure, has brought the customer's offline and online experience together. The common approach for both models - data-driven segmentation, consistency across channels and personalized offers - has become the central hallmark of modern retail CRM (Figure 1) [4].

Figure 1. Conceptual model of a CRM system in a retail enterprise²

Within the framework of the analysis results, the conceptual model proposed by the author included four main layers: a data layer, an omnichannel channel set, an intelligent analytical core, and a customer relationship layer. In this architecture, customer value occupies a central place; each layer forms a closed loop process serving this center. The data layer combines transactional, profile, and contextual data; the channel layer supports live communication with the consumer through the store, mobile application, marketplace, Telegram, and website; the analytical core forms individual offers using segmentation, recommendation, and prediction models; the relationship layer maintains a stable customer return rate with a loyalty program and personalized rewards [11].

The results of the analysis identified three general areas of practice. The first area is unified data management: a retailer should be able to aggregate customer data from different channels into a single profile and make decisions based on this in real time. The second area is personalized recommendations: recommendation systems should analyze the consumer's purchase history, site behavior, and contextual signals and automatically generate a set of individual offers for each customer. The third area is omnichannel consistency: it is necessary to ensure that the customer continues the conversation on the channel in which he started and can easily continue from the point where he left off through another channel. The joint implementation of these three areas has a long-term, positive impact on customer value and loyalty [8].

² Source: compiled by the author based on the results of the analysis.

CONCLUSION AND SUGGESTIONS

The conducted scientific research has shown that modern marketing approaches to customer relationship management in retail enterprises have reached their mature conceptual form as one of the central areas of scientific knowledge. The transition from the classic transactional CRM model to strategic relationship marketing, and from there to the digital ecosystem model based on artificial intelligence and big data, has formed a real growth trajectory of marketing theory. This transition has created new opportunities for retail enterprises: it has expanded the scope of perception of the customer not only as a one-time fulfiller of their needs, but also as a long-term partner and source of value.

The dynamics of the Uzbek retail market and the experience of leading enterprises have confirmed that the country has a strong economic and technological foundation for implementing a digital CRM approach. The fact that the annual growth rate is maintained in double digits, e-commerce is expected to reach a share of about a quarter of the network in a year or two, and the investment strategies of major players such as Uzum and Korzinka, which are focused on customer value, have become practical proof of this position. Such balanced development allows retailers to introduce digital tools in a consistent, phased manner and in a way that is tailored to their business model.

Based on the results obtained, the following practical recommendations were formulated. First of all, it is advisable for retail enterprises to implement a Single Customer View system and consolidate data from all channels into a unified data platform. Second, the gradual integration of personalized recommendation algorithms and predictive analytics modules is an effective way to increase marketing efficiency. Third, it is recommended that loyalty programs be transformed into a multi-dimensional format that includes, in addition to monetary rewards, convenient service, individual offers and emotional connections. Fourth, strategic integration with local marketplaces and banking ecosystems opens up a new growth channel for small and medium-sized retail entities [12].

The scientific significance of the study is that it offers a theoretical generalized model of modern CRM approaches in the country's conditions and provides an opportunity to bring national market experience to the international scientific debate. The practical significance is that the results obtained can be used to solve the problems of improving the marketing strategy of retail enterprises, effectively implementing digital platforms, and sustainably increasing customer value. In future research, it was considered appropriate to empirically evaluate the proposed conceptual model through observations and questionnaires at the scale of real enterprises and to develop differentiated models for individual sectors (food, clothing, household appliances).

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